

Accurate Measurements of Longitudinal-Wave Velocity in IIW-type Calibration Blocks*

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Abstract - A proposed ISO standard specifies tolerances on longitudinal-wave velocity measurements made on IIW-type calibration blocks. These specifications conflict with current ASTM standards for velocity measurements. We evaluate the tolerances of the proposed ISO standard by measuring the longitudinal-wave velocities on a series of blocks, discuss the uncertainties in the measurements, and evaluate the practicality of the proposed standard.

INTRODUCTION

IIW-type (International Institute of Welding) ultrasonic calibration blocks are used widely throughout the world in nondestructive testing of materials and structures. They are used to establish certain physical characteristics of ultrasonic search units (transducers and plastic wedges) and flaw detection systems. Figure 1 illustrates the geometry of a popular U.S. variation of the IIW-type block, the IIW-Type 1 design referenced by ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials). The

Figure 1. ASTM IIW-type calibration block.

geometry and uses of the ASTM design are specified in the ASTM standard E-164. A comprehensive summary of the different block designs is given by Hotchkiss [1].

A proposed European standard, prEN 12223:1995, describes the current European design of the IIW-type block. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is considering adoption of this proposed standard in its current form. The proposed European standard specifies that the longitudinal-wave velocity of the block be measured within $\pm 0.1\%$, or ± 6 m/s, assuming that the block is made of a low-alloy, EN 10025-type steel with a nominal longitudinal-wave velocity of 5920 m/s. In contrast, the current ASTM standard on ultrasonic velocity measurements in materials (ASTM E-494) states that the longitudinal-wave velocity can typically be determined with only a 1% uncertainty for relative measurements, and a 5% uncertainty for absolute measurements. The proposed European standard also specifies that the longitudinal-wave velocities of the total population of steel IIW calibration blocks used by the European NDT service community "shall be within 5920 ± 30 m/s." The corresponding ASTM standard does not specify a tolerance on material velocities in the IIW-type block because a consensus among its voting membership could not be reached. To help harmonize the European and ASTM standards, ASTM subcommittee E-07.06 asked the National Institute of Standards and Technology to make velocity measurements in steel IIW-type calibration blocks, and assist in setting appropriate tolerances for the blocks.

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In this paper, we describe the geometry of the experimental method (pulse-echo), the set of IIW-type blocks used in the study, and the experimental method used to determine the velocities in the blocks (time of arrival). We briefly review two time-of-flight techniques used to determine the longitudinal-wave velocities. We also discuss the known errors affecting our velocity measurements and the uncertainties associated with the measurements. We then state the experimental results, analyze these results and formulate appropriate conclusions regarding the feasibility of the proposed European standard.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD AND SAMPLES

The longitudinal-wave velocities of the blocks were measured using a pulse-echo configuration through the thickness of the blocks. The thickness of each of the blocks was measured with a micrometer to an accuracy of ± 0.0025 mm. Two time-of-flight techniques were used to measure the time delays: the well documented Pulse-Echo Overlap (PEO) method, as described by Papadakis [2], and the First-Arrival-Superposition Technique (FAST), which we developed during the course of this study. FAST is a refinement of a technique described earlier by Eros and Reitz [3].

The sample set of IIW-type calibration blocks being used in our study consisted of 16 blocks, labeled 'A' through 'P'. The sample set included blocks of different age, origin, composition, and design. The chemical composition of most of the blocks was well documented by their owners, with the majority of blocks being 1018, 4340, or A36 low-alloy steels. However, the composition of some of the blocks was unknown.

TIME-OF-FLIGHT MEASUREMENTS

Two time-of-flight measurement techniques were selected to determine the velocities in the blocks: the PEO and FAST methods. The PEO

method was selected because it is frequently used in highly accurate determinations of elastic wave velocities, and can determine these wave velocities to within a very narrow range of uncertainty. The FAST method was selected and refined since first arrival techniques can be easily used in field applications. The PEO measurements were used to establish our best estimates of the block velocities. The details of the implementation of each measurement technique were given in a previous paper [4].

Superficially, the two techniques are very similar in that they both rely on the superposition of successive time waveforms due to back-wall reflections. However, their conceptual origins are quite different. PEO makes use of narrow-band signals and single crystal, unbacked transducers, while FAST is inherently a broadband technique that uses NDT-type transducers. Also, different features of the waveform are utilized in the superposition process. The PEO method overlaps a number of individual cycles in the tone burst. The FAST method overlaps just the first arriving portions of the waveforms, since the earliest arrival of the signal will most likely be the part of the signal least corrupted by material effects such as dispersion and attenuation.

ESTIMATIONS OF UNCERTAINTY

The value of a physical property deduced from experimental measurements must never be considered the "true" value of that property; it is, at best, an estimate of the property taken under those particular experimental conditions. It becomes necessary to first identify and, if possible, correct the measured value for any known errors introduced by the measurement process. The quality of the measurement can then be described in quantitative terms by assigning an uncertainty value to it. Errors in measurements are typically categorized into two classes: errors due to random effects, and errors due to systematic effects.

Both measurement techniques are affected significantly by systematic errors. The narrow-band pulse used in the PEO method makes it possible to estimate systematic errors due to bond thickness and ultrasonic beam diffraction [2]. These systematic errors are usually quite small, each shifting the uncorrected velocity by no more than 10 m/s. The estimated uncertainty associated with each of these systematic errors is ± 5 m/s. Due to the characteristic broadband pulse of the FAST method, it is not currently possible to estimate the systematic errors affecting this technique. However, we are able to estimate the uncertainty introduced to the FAST measurements by systematic errors such as diffraction and the presence of a wear plate on the transducer. The uncertainties due to diffraction and the wear plate are estimated to be ± 35 m/s and ± 71 m/s, respectively.

Random uncertainties in the time-of-flight measurements of both techniques are due mainly to signal processing factors such as the signal/noise ratio, quantization resolution, and sampling rate. The random uncertainty due to these quantities is estimated to be ± 2 m/s for the PEO measurements and ± 17 m/s for the FAST measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A number of measurements were made on each block using the FAST method. Four researchers used the same three transducers, resulting in a total of 12 measurements for each block. Transducers used in this study were all nominally 12 mm in diameter. The center frequency of two of the transducers was nominally 5 MHz (one impedance matched for steel, the other for plastic), while the third was 2.25 MHz (impedance matched for steel). The pulser, receiver, and oscilloscope settings were fixed for each block. Errors and uncertainties directly attributable to the use of different types of transducers and different operators will be reported in a future paper. Only the final uncertainty estimations are reported here.

The longitudinal-wave velocities measured through the 25 mm thickness of the blocks with the FAST method are displayed in Figure 2. The mean value for the 12 measurements made on each block is displayed along with the minimum and maximum values, shown as error bars in the figure. The total uncertainty for each of the velocity measurements is estimated to be ± 80 m/s. The brackets in the upper right hand corner of the figure indicate the proposed tolerance of ± 6 m/s stated in the European draft. As can be seen, the variations between the maximum and minimum velocities exceed the proposed tolerance of ± 6 m/s.

The velocity measurements determined using the PEO method are shown in Figure 3 along with the averages of the FAST measurements. The estimated uncertainty of the PEO measurements is ± 8 m/s. With the exception of block 'O', the averages of the FAST measurements are all lower than the PEO velocity measurements. Since the PEO values are adjusted for systematic errors due to bonding and diffraction, these measurements are a more accurate estimate of the "true" velocities of the blocks. We would expect to see a certain amount of bias in the FAST measurements since they are not corrected for systematic errors. We suspect the systematic errors in the FAST

Figure 2. The mean velocities of the FAST method.

velocities are the reason why the FAST averages are consistently lower than the PEO velocities shown in Figure 3.

CONCLUSIONS

The velocity measurements presented in Figures 2 and 3 now allow us to address the feasibility of achieving two of the proposed tolerances stated in the European draft. It is clear that all of the blocks, with the possible exception of block 'A', would be acceptable reference blocks based on the criterion that the blocks have longitudinal-wave speeds of 5920 ± 30 m/s. However, with the estimated uncertainty of the FAST measurements being ± 80 m/s, little confidence may be placed in any conclusions based only on these measurements.

Determination of the longitudinal-wave velocity to within a $\pm 0.1\%$ (± 6 m/s) tolerance is not practical or reasonable when conventional NDT-type transducers and signal analysis techniques such as the FAST method are implemented. As seen in Figure 2, the variance between the minimum and maximum velocities measured on many of the blocks exceeds the proposed tolerance of ± 6 m/s. Uncertainties in these types of measurements are estimated to be

on the order of ± 80 m/s, where the majority of this overall uncertainty is due to systematic errors like diffraction and wear plate effects, which currently cannot be corrected for.

However, the 0.1% tolerance on longitudinal-wave velocity measurements seems viable when the PEO method is used. The effects of systematic errors due to bond thickness and diffraction can be reduced through theoretical corrections. The major drawback of this measurement technique is the extensive amount of time and technical expertise needed to make the measurement properly. While it has been proven to work very well in the laboratory environment, it is not economical or practical to require field inspectors to implement it.

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Summary of Velocities

Figure 3. Summary of PEO and FAST measurements .